

MILLIY QADRIYATLAR VA MA'NAVIY MEROSNING JAMIYAT TARAQQIYOTIDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya

Ma'lumotlar ruhiy boylik va tarixiy xotiraning jamiyat barqarorligi va rivojiga bo'lgan markaziy rolini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot milliy qadriyatlar xalq ruhi, asrlar davomida shakllangan madaniyat, til, din va urf-odatlar o'rtasidagi aloqani o'rganadi, ularning siyosiy va ta'lim jarayonlaridagi o'rnini tavsiflaydi. Qadriyatlar asrlar davomida tarbiya qadriyatlar mustahkamlab kelgan ruxiy bazaning ifodasidir. Ushbu maqola milliy qiymatlar bo'yicha siyosat ishlab chiqishda ta'lim va madaniyat bilan yoshlar ongini mustaxkamlash yo'llarini ko'rsatadi, merosni himoya qilish uchun indikatorlar muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: mentalitet, madaniy meros, qadriyat, madaniyat, til, din, urf-odatlar, jamiyat, tarixiy xotira, tarbiya.

Annotation

Data explores the central role of spiritual wealth and historical memory in the stability and development of society. The study explores the connection between national values in the spirit of the people, culture, language, religion and Customs formed over the centuries, characterizing their place in political and educational processes. Values are an expression of the spiritual base, which for centuries has strengthened the values of upbringing. This article shows ways to empower youth minds with education and culture in policy making on national values, emphasizing the importance of indicators to protect heritage.

Keywords: mentality, cultural heritage, value, culture, language, religion, traditions, society, historical memory, upbringing.

Kirish

Bugungi globallashuv jarayonida milliy qadriyatlar, urf-odatlar va ma'naviy merosni asrab-avaylash masalasi har qachongidan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Har bir xalqning taraqqiyoti, avvalo, uning milliy o'zligiga, ma'naviy boyligiga tarixiy xotirasiga tayanadi. Milliy qadriyatlar xalq ruhiyatining ko'zgusi,

uning asrlar davomida shakllangan ma'naviy asosidir. Shu bois, milliy o'zlikni saqlash, ma'naviy merosni e'zozlash – jamiyat barqarorligi va taraqqiyotining eng muhim omillaridan biridir. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev ta'kidlaganidek: "Milliy qadriyatlarimiz, ajdodlarimiz merosi biz uchun bebaho bo'lib, ularni asrab-avaylash va yoshlar ongiga singdirish – barchamizning muqaddas burchimizdir." Mazkur fikr zamirida jamiyat taraqqiyotining ildizi milliy o'zlikda, ma'naviy merosni avloddan-avlodga yetkazishda ekanligi yaqqol ifodalanadi.

Metodologiya

Milliy qadriyatlarning tarixiy va falsafiy ildizlari Milliy qadriyatlar xalqning tarixiy taraqqiyoti, urf-odatlar, diniy e'tiqodlari, tili va madaniyatining mahsulidir.¹ O'zbek xalqining qadriyatlari chuqur tarixiy ildizlarga ega bo'lib, ularning shakllanishida qadimiy Turon sivilizatsiyasi, Zardushtiylik davri, Islom madaniyati va Temuriylar davrining ma'naviy merosi alohida o'rin tutadi. Sharq mutafakkirlari – Al-Farobiy, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Navoiy, Jomiy, Bahovuddin Naqshband kabi allomalar o'z asarlarida inson kamoloti, axloq, odob, adolat va ezgulik g'oyalarini ilgari surganlar. Ularning fikrlari milliy qadriyatlarning falsafiy poydevorini tashkil etadi. Milliy qadriyatlar faqat tarixiy xotira emas, balki bugungi kun jamiyatining axloqiy, huquqiy va madaniy me'yorlar tizimidir. Har bir xalqning o'z qadriyatlarini asrab-avaylashi, uni zamon talablari bilan uyg'unlashtira olishi — milliy taraqqiyotning kafolatidir.²

Ma'naviy meros va jamiyat taraqqiyoti o'zaro bog'liqligi Jamiyatning rivojlanishi nafaqat iqtisodiy va siyosiy omillarga, balki ma'naviy asosga ham bevosita bog'liqdir. Ma'naviy meros – bu xalqning asrlar davomida to'plagan tajribasi, bilimlari, e'tiqodi, axloqiy qarashlari va san'ati majmuidir. Bugungi kunda O'zbekistonda milliy merosni o'rganish, uni yoshlar ongiga singdirish maqsadida ko'plab dasturlar amalga oshirilmoqda. "Ma'naviyat va ma'rifat" markazlari, "Yangi O'zbekiston" g'oyasi doirasida olib borilayotgan ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlanmalar bu boradagi muhim qadamdir. Agar jamiyat o'z ma'naviy ildizlarini yo'qotsa, u o'z yo'nalishini ham yo'qotadi. Shu bois ma'naviy merosni chuqur o'rganish va uni yangicha yondashuvda rivojlantirish zamonaviy taraqqiyotning muhim sharti hisoblanadi.

Natijalar va muhokamalar

Yoshlar tarbiyasida milliy qadriyatlarning o'rni Yosh avlod — millatning kelajagi. Ularni milliy ruhda, vatanparvarlik, mehnatsevarlik, halollik, odob-

¹ Najmiddinova M.N. Similarities and differences between values of Uzbek and English cultures // Tanqidiy nazar, tahliliy tafakkur va innovatsion g'oyalar.2025.-B.107-111. <https://phoenixpublication.net/index.php/TANQ/article/view/3802>

² Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2021.

axloq, kattalarga hurmat ruhida tarbiyalash milliy qadriyatlarning eng muhim jihatidir. O‘zbekiston ta’lim tizimida so‘nggi yillarda ma’naviy-ma’rifiy yo‘nalishlarga alohida e’tibor qaratilmoqda. Xususan, maktab va oliy ta’lim muassasalarida “Ma’naviyat soati”, “Vatan tuyg‘usi”, “Tarbiya” fanlari kiritilgan. Bu jarayonlar yoshlar ongida milliy qadriyatlarning mustahkam o‘rnashuviga xizmat qilmoqda.

Milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiyalangan yoshlar har qanday global ta’sirlarga bardosh bera oladigan, mustaqil fikrleydigan, millat manfaatini ustun qo‘yadigan insonlar bo‘lib shakllanadi.³

Rivojlanish omillari va zamonaviy yondashuvlar Bugungi kunda raqamli texnologiyalar asrida ma’naviy meros va qadriyatlarni saqlash yangi shakllarda amalga oshirilmoqda. Virtual muzeylar, onlayn arxivlar, elektron kutubxonalar orqali tarixiy merosni keng ommaga yetkazish imkoniyati mavjud. Shuningdek, zamonaviy ta’lim tizimi orqali qadriyatlarni yosh avlodga yetkazish, ularni zamon ruhida talqin etish dolzarb vazifadir.⁴ Ma’naviyatni faqat so‘z bilan emas, balki amaliy faoliyatda — madaniy tadbirlar, teatr, san’at, adabiyot va ilmiy izlanishlar orqali singdirish zarur. Milliy qadriyatlarni global jarayonlar bilan uyg‘unlashtirish, lekin o‘zligimizni yo‘qotmaslik — yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasining muhim mezonidir.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, milliy qadriyatlar va ma’naviy meros jamiyat taraqqiyotining poydevoridir. Har bir xalq o‘z o‘tmishini chuqur bilib, uni zamonaviy hayotga mos tarzda rivojlantira olsa, barqaror taraqqiyotga erishadi. Bugungi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyoti ham aynan milliy qadriyatlarga, ma’naviy merosga tayanib, zamon bilan hamnafas rivojlanmoqda. Shunday ekan, milliy o‘zligimizni asrash, ajdodlar merosini e‘zozlash va uni yosh avlodga yetkazish – barchamizning muqaddas burchimizdir.

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